

EELISA

European University

**EELISA INNOCORE EELISA MULTI LABS (SHARING FACILITIES
& EQUIPMENT)**

**Deliverable 4.2 - Agreement on the main consensual rules
of access to open facilities**

28/02/2023

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2	16/02/2023	PSL	EELISA InnoCORE quality assurance coordinator (Juan Manuel Munuoz)
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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din București	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This deliverable is the result of the work made in WP4 *EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)*.

The objective of the task was to define the framework conditions for sharing them: minimum time on site, cost of access if any, type of projects, allowed public (researchers, students...). This has been the opportunity to identify barriers to such opening. After discussion within EELISA InnoCORE, it has been suggested that – given the wide diversity of situations – adopting a uniform set of rules would not be possible. Thus, the basic rule for EELISA would be that any EELISA user would be considered as internal user and obey to the local rules applicable to internal users including the decision process to agree on the access of such facility. EELISA will enable more publicity to those internal rules so that researchers when looking for a piece of equipment will know exactly the rules before contacting colleagues.

To fully apply and implement it, this will request internal validation in each member and final endorsement by the Governing Board of EELISA.

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Responsibles for WP4

Partner	Acronym	Contact person for
Universidad Politecnica De Madrid	UPM	Mrs Lidia CEREZO, TTO contact point for scientific and technological services and indicators Web catalogs
Ecole Nationale Des Ponts Et Chaussees	ENPC	Mr. Emmanuel GIRARD, Deputy director of Research Department & Mr. Mustafa SEVIMLI, Project Manager
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nuernberg	FAU	Mr. David SCHKADE, Strategic Projects Department
Istanbul Teknik Universitesi	ITÜ	Mr. Ömer ŞAHİN, Professor
Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Mr Pasqualantonio PINGUE, Head of R&I Area and COO of NEST Laboratory
Scuola Superiore Di Studi Universitari E Di Perfezionamento S Anna	SSSA	Mrs. Rossella RASO, Project Manager
Universitatea Politehnica Din Bucuresti	UPB	Mr Catalin NEGRU, Senior Researcher
Budapesti Muszaki Es Gazdasagtudományi Egyetem	BME	Mr. László LENGYEL, Director of Center for University-Industry Cooperation
Universite Paris Sciences et Lettres	PSL	Mrs. Ilaria CIOFINI, VP Research @ Chimie ParisTech PSL

Review and quality check by EELISA

In order to guarantee coordination and complementarity and avoid overlapping between the two projects, the document has been sent to the EELISA Office.

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

KER. Key Exploitable Results. We refer to the research outputs with major potential for being exploited within the project.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

Research Infrastructures. The term “Research infrastructures” includes any piece of equipment that might be available to a ‘customer’ whether they are in a laboratory (commercial device or developed/customed by researchers themselves), or on a platform.

Research Structures. The term “Research Structures” includes the research centres, research hubs, research groups and research labs, institutes with a research focus, which produce significant research outcomes and thereby, represent a R&I capacity.

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Table of Contents

Technical references	2
Document history	2
EELISA InnoCORE Partners	3
Executive summary.....	4
Responsibles for WP4.....	5
Review and quality check by EELISA	5
Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions	6
Table of Contents.....	7
1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE.....	8
2 Definition.....	10
3 A first mapping.....	10
3.1 Data collection	10
3.2 Results from the survey.....	10
4 Different type of rules.....	12
4.1 Dimensions.....	12
4.2 Principles given by universities	12
5 Setting common rules	12
6 Conclusion and next step.....	12
Annex I – examples of internal rules	14
Price setting at UPM	14

List of figures

Figure 1 - answer to “Do you already have access rules for this facility?”	11
Figure 2 - answer to “What would be your conditions?”	11

List of tables

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders	9
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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 41 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a collective strategic research area and research infrastructure map (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 Definition

By sharing rules of facilities, we mean the set of administrative rules that put conditions on the use of the facilities. It includes:

- The type of activity performed thanks to the facility
- Financial rules (price / cost)
- Safety and security, quality and code of ethics

3 A first mapping

3.1 Data collection

During the work related to D4.1 to list the infrastructure and equipment in laboratories that could be shared within EELISA, specific questions related to sharing rules were asked:

Do you already have access rules for this facility?

- Yes
- No

If yes, where can they be found (website or document):

If not, what would be your conditions:

- For common research project related to EELISA
- For teaching purposes within EELISA
- For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level)
- For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)
- For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project
- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration
- To be agreed in a collaboration agreement
- Other rules

If other, please elaborate your conditions:

3.2 Results from the survey

Thanks to the survey, we received 77 answers from 6 EELISA members excluding UPM who already has a database and did not consult their research for this current work. Indeed, they went through a very similar process 2 years ago to build their database. It was also based on a voluntary work to include facilities in a catalogue so that they can benefit from greater visibility. The information was retrieved from this database.

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Figure 1 - answer to "Do you already have access rules for this facility?"

Figure 2 - answer to "What would be your conditions?"

Flowing the survey, the WP members agreed that a common set of rules would be necessary in order to ease the collaboration via infrastructures as it exists a diversity of answer and most often respondents did not have predefined access rules.

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4 Different type of rules

4.1 Dimensions

The rules defining the possibility to share a facility depend on several dimensions:

- The type of 'customer':
 - o an academic laboratory
 - o a business
- The localisation of the customer:
 - o within the hosting structure of the related facility
 - o within the same University
 - o in the same country / in the European Union
 - o outside the European Union
- The purpose of the collaboration:
 - o Teaching related activity
 - o Research related activity
 - o Innovation and/or commercial activity

4.2 Principles given by universities

When elaborating the sharing rules, it turned that only 2 EELISA members have set up rules at university level: UPM and ITU. It means that in most cases, facility managers or researchers do not have a predefined set of rules when developing collaborations. Example of rules is given in Annex so that managers can get inspired when receiving colleagues.

5 Setting common rules

Considering the diversity of situation, the actual definition of common rules would have been a very long work even if the diversity of situations within EELISA would be limited: requests would come from researchers/academics for research and/or teaching purposes.

In order to overcome this difficulty, it has been suggested to agree on the following basic principle:

Any EELISA researcher or academic requesting access to a piece of equipment hosted in another EELISA member and available in the EELISA catalogue shall be considered as an internal user of this piece of equipment.

By suggesting this simple rule, we ensure that 1) the autonomy of facilities is preserved and 2) all the local and peculiar situations are taken into account. In addition, this rule does not add any administrative step in the process. Being part of EELISA is sufficient to collaborate with other on the same foot.

6 Conclusion and next step

In order to fully implement the rule each institution will have to refer to its own decision making process to identify possible administrative burdens. Indeed, while it would be relatively easy for some facilities and/or situation to consider EELISA members as internal users, other situations might be more difficult to apprehend. All partners will have to review and adopt the rules according to their own legal framework.

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EELISA InnoCORE will rely on two major initiatives 1) the catalogue of infrastructures (D4.1) and 2) the EELISA rule of sharing to develop tools to foster collaboration.

During spring 2023, a pilot call for mobility will be issued so that researchers from EELISA can benefit from funding to organize visits related to an infrastructure that is listed in the catalogue. This will be the first tangible outcome for research community of the work led by WP4. It is also expected that those mobilities help the adoption of the EELISA principle by identify concrete cases of collaborations and needs.

Finally, the group will start the discussion about 'genuine' shared infrastructures where members decide together on the development and management of such infrastructure. Access rules to those infrastructures would immediately implement the EELISA principle. For instance, if 3 EELISA members decide to collaborate on one facility, all EELISA members could be considered as internal users of this facility. The details of this process will be discussed and agreed upon during the upcoming months until the end of the project.

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Annex I – example of internal rules

Price setting at UPM

At UPM, there is a fixed regulation on access to infrastructures or rather technological services. This is what the UPM calls “regulated services” or “fee-for-service” (*servicios tarifados*). There is a fixed method for the calculation of fees. This method includes: depreciation, consumables, repairs, personnel costs, contingencies, indirect costs, TVA (others). Those rules come from both internal UPM rules but also from obligations under national legislation: services must be offered based on prices associated to real costs, so avoiding unfair competition with external organizations offering the same service.

There are two main distinctions for accessing or using infrastructures / technological services:

- a) in-house fee: for stakeholders somehow linked with UPM, e.g. UPM researchers, linked research centres, etc.
- b) external fees: for external stakeholders, companies.

In addition to this, there are special services (*servicios especiales*): ad-hoc services, which come from a negotiation with the company or stakeholder (here both the specific service and the prize are negotiated ad hoc and are part of an agreement); access during night; self-service; flat rate.

Definition of users at Chimie ParisTech PSL

As a federal university, PSL does not have a global policy for its 11 Schools. To illustrate a situation, Chimie ParisTech PSL has already defined different type of users for equipment that is already shared:

Mass Spectroscopy Facility or Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Facility: 3 types of users have been defined:

- Université PSL users
- External academic users
- External non-academic users

When referring to University PSL users, it means that all academics from the other 10 schools of PSL may have access to those facilities hosted and managed by Chimie ParisTech PSL as if they were from Chimie ParisTech PSL. Before the creation of PSL, this was not the case: despite close collaborations between Schools an academic from another School would have been considered as external.

All potential users follow a similar process in accessing the facility and as it provides standard services according to a predefined list of services, the only differences between the categories are the price setting.

